

Multisystemic barriers and facilitators to the adaptation of Colombian Healthcare workers to the pandemic of COVID-19

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Introduction

Adaptation is a dynamic process through which individuals adjust physically, socially, and psychologically to their environment (Michel et al., 2021). These processes become particularly crucial in the face of adverse events such as violence, the loss of loved ones, serious illness, or situations that threaten the integrity of large populations, including war, famine, or natural disasters (Michel et al., 2021). Such highly stressful events are often experienced on a local scale, affecting only certain populations. However, the COVID-19 pandemic, which impacted individuals globally and almost simultaneously, provides a unique opportunity to explore adaptive processes both at the individual and collective levels.

The degree to which individuals experience the pandemic's effects depends largely on their exposure and specific contexts. Healthcare workers occupy a unique position in this crisis, experiencing the pandemic not only as caregivers but also as patients, family members, employees, and members of the general public. This multifaceted involvement has exposed them to significant mental health challenges, including increased depression, anxiety, burnout, work-related stress, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and sleep disorders, along with instances of stigma and violence directed towards them by the civilian population (Munawar & Choudhry,

2021; Osorio-Guzmán et al., 2021; Peñafiel-León et al., 2021; Schneider et al., 2022; Sumner & Kinsella, 2021).

Quantitative studies have shed light on the alarming prevalence of these issues. For instance, a study across several cities in Colombia revealed that 75.61% of healthcare workers reported symptoms of anxiety, 59.18% of depression, and 53.09% experienced stress, with 43.64% presenting symptoms in all three areas (Peñaranda et al., 2022). These figures place Colombia among the countries with the highest prevalence of mental health issues among healthcare workers worldwide.

While these statistics illustrate the scope of the problem, they do not fully capture the complexity of the adaptive processes healthcare workers underwent. To understand these processes in depth, it is essential to move beyond the numbers and explore the lived experiences of healthcare workers. This is particularly important within the framework of Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979), which posits that individuals are influenced by various systems ranging from their immediate environment (microsystem) to broader social and cultural contexts (macrosystem), all interacting over time (chronosystem). Understanding how these systems interact can help identify the barriers and facilitators healthcare workers faced during the pandemic.

Therefore, this study aims to explore the experiences of Colombian healthcare workers, identifying barriers and facilitators to adaptation within the different ecological systems. By focusing on their subjective experiences, we hope to gain a deeper understanding of their coping strategies and the adaptive skills they developed. Ultimately, this study seeks to highlight not

only the hardships faced by healthcare workers but also the collective role we all play in supporting their well-being and ensuring successful adaptation in future crises.

Methods

This qualitative study is part of "Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health of health workers: building resilience in post-conflict territories (HEROES-Colombia)", a comprehensive project that analyzes the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health of healthcare workers. The quantitative component is a longitudinal study with a sample of 2,550 participants to estimate the prevalence and distribution of mental health stressors.

Nineteen semi-structured interviews were conducted with health care workers in different cities of the country between August 2021 and September 2022. Participants were recruited using purposive and snowball sampling techniques, consolidating a sample of general physicians (n=5), specialized physicians (n=4), resident physicians (n=2), head nurses (n=3), auxiliary nurses (n=4) and psychologists (n=1). The purposive sampling, understood as a technique in which people are selected given their specific knowledge and experiences according to the object of research (Oppong, 2013) was done with participants previously identified in HÉROES-Colombia in order to deepen their experiences and to have different cities of the country represented in the sample; therefore, there were interviewees from Medellín (n=6), Bogotá (n=6), Cali (n=5), Rionegro (n=1) and Apartadó (n=1) (See Table 1.). During the interviews, participants were asked about other potential health care workers interested in narrating their work experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic, this in line with the snowball technique, which

is a type of purposive sampling in which other candidates relevant to the object of study are identified (Oppong, 2013).

Table 1. Characteristics of the Study Participants

Participant Characteristics	
Occupation	
General physician	5
Specialized physician	4
Resident physician	2
Head nurse	3
Auxiliary nurse	4
Psychologists	1
Position profile regarding contact with COVID patients	
Frontline workers (ICU, ECU, emergency room)	10
Hospitalization area for non-COVID patients	4
Virtual care for COVID patients	1
Virtual care for non-COVID patients	1
Administrative staff (area coordinators, supervisors, auditors)	3
Residence city	
Medellín	6
Bogotá	6
Cali	5
Rionegro	1
Apartadó	1
Gender	
Men	7
Women	12
Age	
20-30 years old	5
30-40 years old	7
40-50 years old	2
50-60 years old	5
Total	19

The ethical considerations were approved by both the Observational / Interventions Research Ethics Committee from London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, and the Research Bioethics Committee of the National School of Public Health, University of Antioquia. Before starting the virtual interviews, a copy of the informed consent form was sent to each participant's e-mail, which was read and commented before starting the interviews, in order to record in audiovisual form the consent to participate. The audio and video meetings were stored by using codes, and the transcripts were erased in order to protect the identity of the interviewees. When sending the transcripts to the UK researcher, encrypted software was used, accessed only by password to ensure protection.

Initial contact with participants was via email after they responded in the HEROES-Colombia surveys that they were willing to be contacted again by the research team. Since the sample of the quantitative study was so large, priority was given to those who, at the end of the survey, had responded to an open-ended question regarding experiences working during the COVID-19 pandemic. Once they expressed interest by email in proceeding with the study, they were contacted via WhatsApp to agree on the most suitable time for them. From there, 5 participants were interviewed initially, in order to pilot test the topic guide and observe if the answers reflected the formulation of questions made by the team of Colombian and UK researchers. Once these interviews were analyzed, some changes were made to the formulation and order of the topics before proceeding with the rest of the interviews.

The interviews were conducted by a psychologist with previous experience in qualitative research due to the sensitive nature of the topics covered. They were conducted through the Zoom platform, although two of the interviews were conducted by telephone due to connectivity

issues. The interviews lasted approximately 50 to 90 minutes, and were subsequently transcribed, eliminating any information that would reveal the identity of the person or the institution for which he/she worked.

All interviews were transcribed and translated into English. The initial stage of the analysis consisted of taking the first five interviews conducted with the participants in order to construct, from an inductive approach, a framework of analysis with repetitive thematic categories in the speeches. This process was elaborated in a series of virtual meetings with the entire team of researchers, where 12 categories with various sub-themes emerged. Once this analysis map was constructed, two of the researchers coded the five interviews independently to corroborate that the data were represented in the categories. After conducting the rest of the interviews, the transcripts were distributed among the team to develop the rest of the analysis. Throughout this process, there were constant meetings between the researchers to ensure that the coding was rigorous and in line with what the data yielded.

We analyzed our findings based on the Ecodevelopmental theory, identifying the main systems that influenced the adaptation of Healthcare workers in our study.

Findings

The analyses of the interviews surfaced three main systems besides the individual serving as contexts for barriers and facilitators of adaptation of Healthcare workers. At the exosystem level were the government policies, at the mesosystem level were the organizational directives and the reactions of society, and at the microsystem level were all interpersonal relationships. At the core were all individual behaviors, cognitions, emotions, and beliefs.

Exosystem

The exosystem is the outermost layer of all the systems that emerged in this study, with significant influence at all levels but not affected by the actions of a particular individual (ref). Some of the most significant elements in this respect are, the interactions of the health workers with government directives, norms, and protections upon which they do not have a direct effect as individuals. The job guarantees for health workers were commonly mentioned, such as job security, fair salaries, ensuring health workers' safety, provision of protective equipment, and meritocracy. Analyses of the interviews surfaced barriers to adaptation in government policies before and during the pandemic.

When I was finally appointed, there was a change of governor after four years, and he abolished the administrative stream and threw us out of the hospital. A labour massacre took place that year and they removed more than 1,200 people... having passed a merit-based competition.

PARTICIPANT 12.

During the pandemic, strikes exacerbated the lack of protections against stigma, danger, and infection: *[...] the strike was worse. It was terrible here. It wasn't the same all over the country. [...] That day I didn't wear a uniform, so I showed them my ID card and there was a super-important rebel, and only one took pity on my suffering face. It was a terrible time because you didn't know where there were blockades. There were helicopters flying over the city all the time, there was nowhere to buy things, the city was destroyed. It was very tough. .* *PARTICIPANT 13*

Yes, there was a moment of very horrible social pressure. This was when, the health system itself told us that we couldn't wear our uniform for our own protection. Because there was a time when

society said that we were the ones who carried the virus. So it was very difficult for you to have to put your uniform away and begin to camouflage yourself, and for people not to realize what you were doing and what line of work you were in. PARTICIPANT 6

On the other hand, the decision to prioritize health workers for vaccination was seen as a facilitator of adaptation: *The other thing is the vaccine. Well, I know that if I am vaccinated it's not going to completely prevent me from getting the virus, but it does reduce the risk of me dying. And so we were the first ones to get vaccinated, so then they told us like "Okay, we're going to give you a lifeline in the meantime." So that did go down a lot. PARTICIPANT 2*

Health workers perceived insufficient protection by the government but appreciated some of the efforts that were made, which reduced stress and facilitated their interaction in different systems. Also, it was identified that some of the barriers in the government dimension such as lack of protection, were sometimes alleviated by other systems, such as the work environment:

I think that had a lot to do with each employer. I think if we had stayed with the health system alone, we wouldn't have been able to sustain ourselves. I think what really helped us was each workplace, and how they managed to implement what little they had, but no, I think the health system fell a little short in the end.. PARTICIPANT 16

Mesosystem

The mesosystem is more permeable than the exosystem, but it still has more effect in the individual than vice versa.

Organizational and work-related

Health workers accounts include several aspects of their work conditions, beginning with their activities, such as exhausting shifts, excessive pandemic standards, denial of medical leave, unequal treatment of certain personnel, and injustice. Additionally, they discussed the availability of resources like infrastructure and PPE.

A common topic among health workers was the difficulties presented by the long shifts and how they impacted their health and their relationships with their families:

No, you don't have time. And when do you go to the bathroom? Never. It would be ten hours without going to the toilet, ten hours without taking a sip of water, we didn't have time.

PARTICIPANT 15

You were busy, busy all the time. Your turn. 'I can't take off my mask for my family's safety, I can't take off my mask, I can't take off anything for my family's safety.' And there's no way I can say that I'm going to have a bottle of water in the break that they supposedly gave us, which didn't exist, because it was eight hours, it was shifts of eight hours. 'Come on, come on', as soon as you arrived. And they would give me two hours after my coming off shift to finish all the administrative work, because you couldn't cope with so many patients. So it was difficult, it was difficult for me.

PARTICIPANT 15

They called me to tell me that she had had another heart attack and that I should come down immediately. I wondered if she had died and they needed me to come down to sign something. I didn't tell anyone, because my dad was in ICU on one side, and my sister and niece in isolation and unable to do anything. [...] I went to tell the boss that I needed to go down. She told me: "You've got a patient about to come in. You have to take responsibility for your work activities and you can't go down". I told her: "i don't give a shit what you think, i'm going down now". I

threw my things at her and left. I thought they were going to throw me out, but I went down anyway. They were resuscitating her.. PARTICIPANT 14

Other barriers to adaptation in the work environment were the inflexibility and repercussions of disobeying hospital directives and the disregard for the mental health and wellness of Healthcare workers:

What we feared the most, and what always happened, was reprisals with regard to the workload. On one occasion I went to talk to her about things I didn't like. Two days later I came on rounds and saw that I had the heaviest assignment possible. She left me like that for the whole week. In the end, it was like smearing Vaseline on your face so that everything slid off . Then I finally decided to assume that this was the way things were, and I was satisfied with the fact that I had a job with very good pay.PARTICIPANT 14

[...] when the pandemic began, they forgot about us a lot because there wasn't... I'm talking as far as the hospital, there wasn't support from Human Resources. There was no support for the staff; everything was punitive, everything was restrictive, everything was about fear..

PARTICIPANT 2

And I think it's tiredness. Tiredness. Sometimes you have to find, let's say, how to moderate it. You cannot be tired. And I think that we have shown here, in our group of colleagues, that everyone, everyone is completely tired, so that is one aspect, a very complicated situation. And in this, let's say in this district, in this public network, I think they try to make welfare programmes, but they don't achieve anything. So you are just working. Doing your hours and that's it. And that also makes you, mentally, I think, worn out by that situation. PARTICIPANT 18

However, it is important to note that these barriers were not generalized in all workplaces, with some implementing policies to care for their workers' mental health and conditions, giving them renewed appreciation for their jobs and their purpose.

Let's say that, if we talk in terms of hiring, it is one of the institutions that hire for an indefinite term. During the pandemic they gave us the family day off, the day of the pandemic, the day of I don't know what else. In other words, a number of things they gave us in addition to what they had already given us. [...] They managed everything very quickly. And let's say that makes you say "the organization is giving me things that are beneficial and I, in the end, I give them something back". PARTICIPANT 8

I believe that, if it hadn't been for the entire healthcare system (not only the doctors) facing the pandemic (even though the figures are not very encouraging for me), things could have been worse and catastrophic. And I'm not just talking about doctors, I think I'm talking about administrators, about being contingent, managing to set up intensive care units, scheduling things, having nurses be more or less trained and everything. I see that a lot of the things that we thought couldn't be done, can be done. PARTICIPANT 1

Society

The interaction of health workers with society included the perceptions of the role of health workers, disregard of precautions, the stigma, the violence, the news, the misinformation, as well as the support.

The disregard of precautions led to frustration and angst, and constituted a barrier against adaptation: *It was frustration. It was very frustrating, like, 'I really could do it, but I don't know [how]', so it was like being tied up, like being against a wall. And above all, it made you feel anguished, uneasy. It was disheartening to be stuck here day and night with a gown, gloves, a mask, visor, with all those things, and everyone partying while the peak goes up, up, and up.*

PARTICIPANT 19

In addition, stigma and misinformation led to significant fear in health workers: *It was very tough when people said that we were charging 30 million pesos... that feeling of: "You are exposing yourself for them, and as a result, you are [seen as] a murderer and corrupt person who sells patients and kills them for money?" And that you have to hide because if they know you are a doctor they will treat you badly... that was one of the worst things that could have happened.* *PARTICIPANT 13*

Stigma and misinformation were not only barriers by themselves, but they also brought about serious consequences such as discrimination or violence against the health workers' integrity.

I was on the metro and a woman was next to me (the seat was empty) and I got on and sat down and the woman looked at me with those eyes like, like when you're really annoyed. She stood up and left, and that day I felt literally, like the worst thing in the world. *PARTICIPANT 2*

One day, we were on duty and the alarms went off. "XXX Hospital is on alert." When that is activated, everybody has to be on the alert. When they warned us, it was because in the emergency department there were around 100 people trying to break down the door because they wanted to attack the healthcare workers because we were killing people. And inside I was

thinking “Oh my God, it’s true; it’s that the people outside don’t understand what is going on here inside, and it’s a myth that we’re charging 30 million for each person who dies from the pandemic.” PARTICIPANT 2

Microsystem

The microsystem equally affects and is affected by the individual. The microsystem strongly influences the perception of barriers and facilitators in all systems, being the most determinant system in adaptation. The microsystem is the most influential level of the ecological systems theory.

Interpersonal relationships

The perception of barriers and facilitators to the adaptation of health workers was strongly influenced by relationships with family, friends, coworkers, patients, and others.

Patients

Health workers were uncertain about the virus and the progress of the disease, which affected their interaction with patients. They had to prioritize the recipients of services and deal with the death of patients, as well as manage the reactions of patients and their relatives. Health workers can enhance their ability to adapt by personalizing patient care. By acknowledging the unique needs and characteristics of each patient, health workers can cultivate a sense of purpose and meaning in their work.

Part of my salary goes to giving things to those with leukaemia, because obviously they don't want to eat. Mainly because COVID makes them lose their sense of smell and taste. I go in and ask them what their dream food is. They say refried beans. My mum makes them and I take them in. That's what I do for catharsis. PARTICIPANT 12

It was exhausting. I think that by that point, the nursing staff was exhausted. And at that point, I don't know if they had lost their sensitivity, or had reached a level of dehumanisation in the face of death, because they'd say, 'No, boss, he's going to die'. But he could be my father, he could be my grandfather, he could be my son. So it affected me a lot.. PARTICIPANT 15

"Damn it, my having delayed, my not spending more time with that patient, my not keeping an eye on him could have been a cause of the patient's death. It was like, "Could it be that I too was to blame and didn't notice? Or did I notice and but couldn't do anything about it?" PARTICIPANT 2

Direct interaction with patients were also seen as facilitators of adaptation:

And I sit down with the patient and say to him something like, "Tell me what your day-to-day is like, tell me about your life." And the patient begins to tell me things, and I, like I really enjoy that, a lot ... One of them said to me, "Hey, thank you so much for not skipping your shift and for coming to take care of us", and you're like, "Hey, cool." It was like motivation. PARTICIPANT 2

Coworkers

Among the challenges faced by health workers was the unequal distribution of responsibilities between doctors and nurses. Additionally, the whole team was dealing with fatigue, making it harder to collaborate effectively.

And the mothers, as always, smile for the doctor and say that the child is better. When he leaves, the nurse always gets all the frustration from the mother. When the doctor leaves, they stop smiling and the mistreatment is aimed at the nursing service. You try to do everything humanly possible. PARTICIPANT 12

Death of coworkers:

We had a classmate who was really brainy. He graduated with us, specialised in internal medicine, and had been a nephrology graduate for about two or three months (he was already in his subspecialty). He was working as an internist, and he caught COVID and died about a week later. And we were like... I think that was a big blow... PARTICIPANT 16

We found a completely desolated emergency team. Doctors were crying, nurses were crying, and everyone was saying that they didn't want to continue working, that they didn't want to work in those conditions. [...] Something crazy happened. The doctors started to say "this is really serious". And when they took him out in the hearse, nobody could go with him because we were talking about the first one, nobody could go with him. PARTICIPANT 8

They found ways to support each other and work together to overcome these barriers:

We have formed a nice group because we can't go out, and every month we all collect money together and I go and buy coffee, sugar, milk, biscuits... so in that way we work very well, because we are the only ward in the hospital that has our own cupboard. They gave us a fridge and a microwave... so it's like there are very few of us, we are locked up, but we make a good team with the mothers, with the children... and we make it nice in there. In the end we've been a family for two years. PARTICIPANT 12

Family and Friends

The responsibility of caring for their family and friends sometimes led to an increase of the burden. However, in family and friends health workers also found their main sources of relief and purpose.

And at that point in my care, I was kind of emotional because my family was unwell with COVID. So as I was the only doctor on my mother's side of the family, and obviously there were friends and relatives on my father's side, so it was like, 'I'm ill, what can I do?' So it was the burden of work, and the burden of home, and the burden of family. 'What can I do? What can I take? I'm not well, can you come and see me?'. PARTICIPANT 17

That time was very difficult for me, but it was also a very important time for me to work out which people would still be part of my life, and which would not. I got a lot out of it. There were people who were very busy, but who sent a message of encouragement. There were family members who sent me money for nappies. Others sent groceries to my house. I was happy in that sense, but even though I earn well and everything, it's nice to have help. PARTICIPANT 14

Apart from that, well the people who were close to me, who gave me support every day, with their words. And friends: in November I managed to get in touch with friends. Not only by phone because obviously you can hear someone's voice, but when you can see the person and have a face-to-face conversation, it's a big change.. PARTICIPANT 17

Individual

At the individual level, the main barrier to adaptation of adaptation was the significant stress suffered by health workers, which affected their daily routines, their sleep, increased anxiety, and fear, many times leading to mental health problems.

At night and in the morning I would break down in tears. I would lock myself in the bathroom, have a bath and cry so that my wife wouldn't see me and realise, because when you have a bath you wash your face and come out with red eyes, so if she asks, "Oh, why are your eyes red?", I can say, "Oh, I just got soap in my eyes".PARTICIPANT 9

And you just have to grit your teeth. I'd go to bed at night and think about the patient, dream about doing intubations, dream about doing thousands of things. I even thought about taking some time off, because I thought, "What am I doing? People are dying and there's nothing I can do about it". PARTICIPANT 9

Because there comes a point when you start to have these ideas about passive death, like, look, I was in the car, saying, 'Am I going to make it? Am I going to drive off the road? Am I going to crash? Maybe that roof might fall on me.' It was like those ideas – I didn't have anything structured as such, but it was powerful. [...], I asked a lot of people, and they were like, 'Yeah, I'm like that too'.PARTICIPANT 19

Sleep, no. I think I've lost that one. The doctor changed me to a tablet called trazodone, and that doesn't help me sleep. Because he wants to take me off the zopiclone that I take. So it fills me with anxiety because I take the trazodone and I don't fall asleep. I start to look at the clock, I see that it is 12:30 and that I have 5 hours left to sleep, and then I have a 12-hour shift. Then the anxiety doesn't let me sleep.. PARTICIPANT 12

Because of the nature of their work, for health workers, isolation was a significant barrier to adapt to the new situation; some describe it as the hardest part of the pandemic.

But staying in four walls... and at that time I was almost alone in the house because of the fear and all that, it drove me crazy and I had someone to talk to and what to do. I used to say: "People who had to stay locked up for a long time are very thick". You don't know how the children survived so long locked up. Because I tell you, one week and I was already crazy. That made me crazier than anything else in the hospital, being in isolation. PARTICIPANT 10

Personally, the most critical moment was when we were sent home. We were very high risk. I didn't ask for it, or request the appointment, but they reviewed everyone's CVs, looked at our ages and saw that I was 55 years old, had some comorbidity (I've had hypertension since I was 27 and I was fatter then than I am now), and the occupational doctor decided that I had to leave. That was terrible for me.. PARTICIPANT 11

And importantly, the fear of contagion:

[...] the magnitude was huge. And going to the Intensive Care Unit was hell. What used to be a room for one person, became a room for two, three people. People intubated in the corridors. So you went in there with all those things on you, well, with a sense of anguish because you didn't know if you had washed well or not, if you had changed your mask or not, if you had touched your nose while caring for these patients. PARTICIPANT 4

Among the main facilitators were successful adaptation to previous stressful experiences. *This is the reason I've always tried to be very calm with things. Because you can't let your mind be poisoned by so many things that happen around you. Rather you need to learn to bear them in a more peaceful manner for your own health.* PARTICIPANT 5

My being from this neighborhood and growing up in this neighborhood, what has it taught me. That I have to get busy, that if I sit around feeling sorry for myself, that if I keep focusing on negative things, if I keep fearing, I won't move forward. Because just as I grew up in this neighborhood, and am a survivor, and have already reached adulthood, that's how I was able to make it in this pandemic. PARTICIPANT 2

The development of mental health problems was a clear indicator that in many cases, the barriers were stronger than facilitators, and coping mechanisms were insufficient or inadequate to deal with the new situations.

Around the time I was working in that institution, I lost about 12 kilos. I didn't sleep, as I told you, I developed a very strong depression, issues with anxiety. 'Quick, run, get on with it, quick, go on', all the time. Not eating, not sleeping, until one day my daughter said, 'No mum, you look really bad, let's go to A&E'.. PARTICIPANT 15

It was the first time I was incapacitated, diagnosed with burnout and associated severe anxiety and depression. I was incapacitated for two months, the medication really didn't suit me so I started to have a really strange adverse reaction to the fluoxetine. It usually makes people alert, but it made me drowsy. Anger. Extraordinary anhedonia... I started getting suicidal ideations and started to plan it. I even put something in place.. PARTICIPANT 13

Among the main adaptive skills developed were:

Recognizing their own humanity and vulnerability:

[...] sometimes we forget that the mind is one of our organs; that we can get ill. So for me to accept that I had become unwell in my psyche, that I was being hospitalised and treated, and that

I should not feel ashamed, you know? Maybe I'm not as strong, or maybe I'm stronger than a lot of people thought but I couldn't handle it like a lot of people. PARTICIPANT 15

Recognising ourselves as vulnerable beings too, with the power to do good to a patient, but with the capacity to do a lot of harm to ourselves as professionals. Because we tell the patient, 'You have to sleep, you have to eat, you have to rest, you have to do things'. But we are not capable of doing it ourselves. Do you realise that? So we are the most incoherent professionals.

PARTICIPANT 15

..to realise that you are vulnerable and not Superman. You have to keep your feet on the ground and stay grounded all the time. To recognise that you are vulnerable not only because of depression but also because of Covid, which shows us that there are young people, vaccinated, who are dying. PARTICIPANT 13

Learning to compartmentalize, dealing with the problems in the moment.

Well, I usually try to leave all the hospital problems there. I always say "when I leave my house, this is where the hospital problems start". And when I leave the hospital, it's there. It doesn't mean that one doesn't feel sorry, I do remember the patient... but I do try... but sometimes one tries to depersonalize because otherwise I think that... that's why it was very hard for more than one of us, because we all have different personalities; but at that moment it's horrible. You feel bad. You say "I could almost be sentencing to death one over the other", but it's not my fault either, because that's what we have. PARTICIPANT 10

Trust and positivity through spirituality:

Well, it's down to each individual. How you work spiritually. I mean, before 2020 I didn't worry so much about that, but now I worry more about spirituality. What each person believes in, if they have a religion, or if they believe in something else, then [they should] dedicate some time to it. PARTICIPANT 17

I try to lead a spiritual life, and this has helped me a lot; because I say that you always have to have faith, to trust something, regardless of the way you think or of the way you act, you must believe in something. I mean, it can be in anything, I say that's what faith is, to believe in something. PARTICIPANT 6

Seeking help, with professionals or support with coworkers and friends:

The day programme helped me a lot. I liked that I could go away, come back, talk and everything. So like being able to talk, to be able to say, 'I'm more than just a COVID nurse, I'm more than that'. To be able to talk about... How can I explain it? About what was happening in a more human way, and in a way that was more distant from your surroundings. How to get away from the unit, from death. And to see that in reality, what was being done, was what needed to be done. PARTICIPANT 15

Well, personally, I discovered like psychological therapy in a support I received approximately 3 or 3 and a half years ago. And with my psychologist I kind of talk about those stressful things, like "I lost control, I didn't know what to do". So, let's say that with that, in my personal work, let's say that I have also made way there. PARTICIPANT 4

The strategy was collective psychology, I mean, talking to your colleagues, that allows you to let off steam and come back. PARTICIPANT 9

Recognition of impossible standards placed on health workers:

[...] Because we are not strengthening mental health in health professionals, why are there still no real programmes so that health professionals can be treated as human beings who can get ill? No, health professionals must continue to cut out their emotions, because they are heroes, heroes without a cape. PARTICIPANT 15

Power and capacity:

“And I haven't had any symptoms that I know of. If I did get it, I never realized it and I've never been placed in isolation, because it's a particular point of pride. It was like “Damn, I made it through this pandemic and didn't die.” PARTICIPANT 2

Discussion

We focused our analyses on the three systems, other than the individual, that emerged from the healthcare workers' accounts: the exosystem, mesosystem, and microsystem. Each of these systems had varying impacts on their ability to adapt during the pandemic. The exosystem included government policies, the mesosystem encompassed work and society, and the microsystem involved all their interpersonal relationships with coworkers, friends, patients, family, and others. Although intertwined with all the systems, the chronosystem and macrosystem were not as clearly elucidated in the interviews.

As expected, the closer the components of the systems were to the individuals, the more significant their perceived effect on the adaptation processes during the pandemic. The barriers or facilitators in the closest components of the systems, mainly the microsystem—interpersonal relationships—appeared to influence the perception of barriers and facilitators in other systems and were thus crucial in their adaptation to the pandemic. This is evident in cases of being attacked, receiving family support, help from others, and having positive interactions with patients, among others.

The exosystem, represented by government policies for the health system before and during the pandemic, was perceived as a source of frustration, including the term “work massacre,” possibly because it was the system over which individuals had the least control. Furthermore, previous negative or positive experiences within the health system were exacerbated in isolation. Relief provided by government policy, such as prioritizing healthcare workers for vaccination, came several months after they had already been exposed to various and continuous sources of stress. Other aspects of the pandemic, such as protection against stigma and prioritizing their safety, could have been better addressed before the vaccine.

Perceptions within the mesosystem, which included the organizations they worked for and the general society, were mixed. Common barriers to adaptation were exhausting and inflexible work conditions, and stigma and violence from members of society. Thus, the main facilitators of adaptation were improved work conditions and directives to protect their safety and mental health. In some cases, the mesosystem acted as a relief from inadequate government policies to protect healthcare workers from contagion, violence, and exhaustion.

Similar to the exosystem, healthcare workers' accounts indicated they had little influence over their work conditions or societal treatment. However, due to the nature of their work, they had the most direct experience with changing strategies and public reactions. They were also the main witnesses to improvisations and achievements as events unfolded. This makes their perspective on the pandemic more complex and nuanced than the experiences of workers in other sectors. Not only do healthcare workers' conditions need substantial adjustments for society as a whole to adapt to highly disruptive situations, but also the communication between work and society and healthcare workers must improve. Change can start by providing spaces where their lived experiences are valued. Healthcare workers found it easier to adapt to the pandemic in environments where they felt heard.

The microsystem, reflecting interpersonal relationships, had the greatest perceived effect on healthcare workers' adaptation processes. Negative experiences within this system, such as mistreatment by coworkers, supervisors, or relatives, could trigger a breakdown caused by frustration with work conditions or government policies. Positive experiences, such as support from family members or friends, appreciation from patients, and collaboration with coworkers, significantly influenced their perception of their capacity to overcome barriers and facilitators in other systems.

A notable power dynamic within the microsystem revealed in the interviews was the persistent hierarchy in the face of danger. Doctors' safety was sometimes prioritized over that of nurses. Nurses, who generally have more direct contact with patients, were expected to take more risks and were sometimes "abandoned" as the sole care providers. This uneven distribution of responsibilities led to frustration and feelings of underappreciation, constituting a significant

barrier to their adaptation. This power dynamic, where those of higher ranks are valued more than those in lower ranks, exists in all societies. However, facing contagion and potential death made this dynamic more noticeable and potentially more devastating for mental health than in other situations.

From healthcare workers' accounts, isolation was one of the hardest parts of the pandemic. Although fear of infecting themselves and loved ones added to the burden, as social beings, feeling excluded from the rest of the community was a significant source of anxiety, depression, and insomnia. This evokes a sense of "disconnectedness" at a time when we were acutely aware of how connected we are and how our actions could affect even those not in close proximity. Most of the barriers faced by healthcare workers could have been mitigated if more robust support networks had been in place and more collective efforts had been made to use that global connection to our advantage.

Individual beliefs, personal characteristics, and previous experiences with crises were crucial in creating or strengthening adaptive skills. However, the development of mental health problems in countless healthcare workers indicates that, in many cases, the barriers were stronger than the facilitators, and coping mechanisms were insufficient or inadequate to deal with the new situations.

Our study highlights the importance of promoting resilience within the health system. A resilient health system learns from the experiences of healthcare workers to implement protocols that drive changes across all levels to anticipate consequences. A resilient health system does not place the responsibility of facing a crisis solely on its healthcare workers, expecting them to

manage their perceptions and relationships, improve their health-seeking behaviors, and, above all, be heroic.

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